

1 **A curated dataset for cryo-EM map post-processing**

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13 ***Abstract***

14 Cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM) has become a fundamental technique in structural
15 biology, and the assessment of post-processing methods remains a challenge due to the
16 limited availability of widely adopted standardized and reproducible resources. In this
17 work, we present a curated dataset—carefully divided into non-overlapping training,
18 validation, and test subsets—that includes half-maps, average maps, fitted atomic
19 models, and post-processed volumes generated using a diverse set of approaches,
20 including Deep Learning methods such as CryoTEN, EMReady, EMReady2, and
21 DeepEMhancer. The dataset is accompanied by precomputed quality metrics derived
22 from Phenix tools and Q-scores, enabling quantitative and comparable evaluation of
23 map–model agreement as well as global and local structural quality across different
24 post-processing methods. Leveraging this standardized resource, we have performed, to

25 the best of our knowledge, the first independent and comprehensive comparative
26 benchmark of state-of-the-art cryo-EM post-processing methods. In addition, we also
27 provide a unified workflow and the code used for metric computation, allowing
28 researchers to apply the same evaluation framework to their own methods and ensure
29 reproducible, fair comparisons. Overall, this dataset and evaluation framework provide
30 a robust foundation for benchmarking post-processing methods, especially those based
31 on Deep Learning and support the development of new cryo-EM map enhancement
32 strategies.

33 ***Keywords***

34 Cryo-EM, curated dataset, post-processing, Phenix, Q-scores, fair comparison

35

36 ***1. Introduction***

37 Cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM) has emerged as a key method in structural biology
38 due to its ability to determine 3D maps of macromolecular complexes from 2D
39 projection images. Over the past decade, methodological and computational advances
40 have driven significant progress toward achieving resolutions below 3Å, enabling the
41 construction of increasingly accurate and detailed atomic models. In this context, map
42 resolution plays a critical role, as it not only defines the level of observable detail, but
43 also directly influences the quality of the derived models and their structural validation.

44 To ensure the reliability and reproducibility of these structural models, dedicated
45 public repositories have been established. The Protein Data Bank (PDB) [1] serves as a
46 fundamental repository of atomic models obtained from structural modalities, including
47 cryo-EM, and provides validation tools and standardized reports. Complementing it, the
48 Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) [2] stores cryo-EM volumes and tomograms
49 of macromolecular complexes and subcellular structures obtained through diverse
50 techniques. More recently, the Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR)
51 [3] has emerged as a repository for raw cryo-EM and cryo-ET datasets. Together, these
52 databases provide the main resources for data deposition, validation, and reuse in
53 structural biology. Utilizing these data, numerous studies, including those based on
54 artificial intelligence, have explored new computational strategies to enhance cryo-EM
55 maps. Methods such as DeepEMhancer [4] and EMReady [5] apply Deep Learning
56 (DL) methodologies to process raw data maps, highlighting structural features,
57 facilitating interpretation, and demonstrating how automated approaches can improve
58 both the visual and structural quality of maps.

59

60 Training DL methods for cryo-EM tasks requires carefully curated data that
61 could enable effective training of the model. Depending on the application, different
62 data sources are needed, for example, micrographs with particle coordinates for particle
63 picking, or experimental maps and corresponding atomic models for map enhancement
64 and structural interpretation. However, one of the main challenges in developing DL
65 approaches for cryo-EM is the selection and preparation of appropriate training data, as
66 raw datasets often contain redundancy, noise, or inconsistencies in processing. Several
67 datasets have been proposed to support DL applications in cryo-EM, such as CryoPPP
68 [6] for particle picking and a dataset by Giri et al. [7] for map enhancement. Following
69 the same rationale, we present a new curated dataset designed to facilitate the training,
70 validation, and benchmarking of DL models for cryo-EM map processing.

71 Our dataset provides a comprehensive collection of raw maps, together with
72 their corresponding half-maps and atomic models, which are already split into non-
73 overlapping and non-redundant training, validation, and test subsets (please see section
74 2.4 Data availability and information). This careful partitioning ensures data
75 independence and allows the development of robust and unbiased DL models without
76 requiring users to manually curate or split the data. In addition, the dataset includes
77 maps post-processed with state-of-the-art enhancement methods (see Section 2.1. *Post-*
78 *processing methods*) and their evaluation with current metrics, enabling direct
79 comparison between techniques. What distinguishes this dataset from previous ones is
80 that it also provides precomputed quantitative metrics and the processed maps
81 themselves, allowing users to evaluate and compare their own DL models against
82 standardized references. As map resolution alone does not fully capture the overall
83 quality of a cryo-EM reconstruction, we incorporate objective structural metrics into the
84 evaluation pipeline, establishing a robust quantitative basis for the analysis of post-

85 processing methods. This is important because an effective post-processing can
86 substantially enhance the interpretability of density maps, improving both structural and
87 functional insights beyond mere sharpening. Furthermore, we provide the code used to
88 compute all these metrics in our GitHub repository, so that researchers can apply the
89 same evaluation procedure to their own results and obtain directly comparable
90 performance measures, ensuring full reproducibility and fairness across different
91 approaches.

92 ***2. Materials and methods***

93 In this section we present the post-processing methods used, the quantitative metrics
94 employed in the dataset and the unified validation workflow presented in this work. We
95 also describe how these metrics are integrated into the evaluation pipeline and provide
96 an overview of the dataset.

97 **2.1. Post-processing methods**

98 In recent years, the incorporation of AI into cryo-EM map processing has led to the
99 development of powerful tools designed to improve structural interpretability of density
100 maps. These methods have shown considerable promise, providing cleaner and more
101 informative reconstructions that may facilitate atomic-level model building and
102 analysis, albeit they could potentially introduce artifacts. To offer a fair comparative
103 between these methods, we applied several post-processing approaches across our
104 dataset, each representing a distinct strategy for enhancing cryo-EM maps.

105 **2.1.1. LocScale**

106 LocScale [8] introduced the first voxel-wise sharpening strategy for cryo-EM maps, in
107 contrast to conventional approaches based on a single global B-factor. This approach is
108 a deterministic, model-based local amplitude-scaling procedure that uses prior atomic

109 models to rescale Fourier amplitudes while preserving experimental phases. Thus,
110 LocScale is not a deep-learning method, but a model-dependent post-processing
111 procedure. We first executed LocScale using its default parameters, then, we ran the
112 algorithm a second time adjusting the resolution values for each map; this new version
113 is referred to as LocScale*. When the reference model is accurate, LocScale can
114 enhance the visibility of structural features by adjusting local amplitudes. However, its
115 performance depends on the quality of the input model, and incorrect fits may introduce
116 bias into the sharpened density.

117 **2.1.2. LocSpiral**

118 LocSpiral [9] performs voxel-wise local sharpening by analysing local amplitudes and
119 retaining only those map details whose signal is significantly above the estimated noise.
120 Unlike methods that rely on deep learning or on atomic models as references, LocSpiral
121 uses only information intrinsic to the experimental map and therefore does not introduce
122 model-dependent bias or hallucination artefacts. This makes it especially useful during
123 early stages of structural analysis or when no reliable atomic model is available. By
124 adapting the sharpening strength to the local signal-to-noise characteristics, LocSpiral
125 improves the visual interpretability of maps while preserving high-confidence structural
126 features.

127 **2.1.3. DeepEMhancer**

128 DeepEMhancer [4] was the first deep learning-based method specifically developed for
129 cryo-EM map post-processing. It was trained on pairs of experimental maps (obtained
130 by averaging deposited half-maps) and corresponding LocScale-sharpened maps
131 computed using the associated atomic models [8]. By using LocScale outputs as
132 learning targets instead of densities directly simulated from atomic models,
133 DeepEMhancer benefits from model-guided sharpening but avoids the stronger model

134 bias that would arise from training directly on purely model-derived maps. At inference
135 time, DeepEMhancer operates only on the experimental map and does not require an
136 atomic model as input, producing maps with enhanced contrast and detail that can
137 facilitate visual interpretation.

138 **2.1.4. EMReady**

139 EMReady [5] is a DL-based post-processing method that employs a hybrid Swin-Conv-
140 UNet architecture integrating both local and non-local feature modeling. Trained on
141 simulated maps generated from PDB atomic structures, it reduces the influence of
142 experimental noise and enhances the interpretability of cryo-EM densities. Its successor,
143 EMReady2 [10], introduces a resolution-dependent post-processing strategy that adapts
144 the target to be sensitive to atomic model local quality, improving the balance between
145 noise reduction and preservation of high-resolution details. Both versions report
146 improvements in global and local quality metrics, such as FSC, Q-score and map-model
147 correlation, and can assist the visual steps of model interpretation, while requiring
148 standard validation against unprocessed half-maps.

149 **2.1.5. CryoTEN**

150 CryoTEN [11] is a DL model based on a U-Net architecture with Transformer blocks
151 and Efficient Paired Attention (EPA) [12], designed for cryo-EM map enhancement. It
152 was trained to reproduce, from a given input map, the associated atomic model in the
153 training set, hence, at inference, only the input map is required. Its application has been
154 shown to produce improvements in key metrics such as Fourier Shell Correlation (FSC),
155 Q-score, and map-model correlation, thereby facilitating further map interpretation.

156 2.2. Metrics

157 To assess the impact of each post-processing method on map quality, our dataset
158 includes a set of precomputed metrics that quantify map–model agreement and evaluate
159 local map reliability both globally and in specific regions. To calculate these metrics,
160 we used established tools from the Phenix package [13] such as *real_space_refine*,
161 *mtriage*, and *emringer*. In addition, we included the map Q-scores [14], which
162 compliments the overall evaluation by providing detailed information on the
163 resolvability of individual atoms within the processed map. All calculated metrics,
164 together with the intermediate files produced during their computation, are archived in
165 our dataset. This organization guarantees complete reproducibility of the analyses and
166 provides direct access to quantitative results along with the relevant structural data for
167 additional evaluation or benchmarking. For more information, please see Section 2.4.
168 *Data availability and information.* A description and comprehensive interpretation of
169 the metrics are provided in Tables S1, S2, and S3 in the supplementary material.

170 2.2.1. Phenix.mtriage

171 We used *phenix.mtriage* [9], [13] from the Phenix package with both post-processed
172 and unprocessed cryo-EM maps. This tool provides a comprehensive evaluation of map
173 and model quality through three distinct categories of metrics:

- 174 **1. Map-based resolution metrics**, such as *d_fsc_half_maps*, which estimates
175 global map resolution between half-maps, and d99-based metrics (*d99*,
176 *d99_half_map1*, *d99_half_map2*), which quantify the highest spatial frequencies
177 that contain non-negligible signal amplitude in the maps
- 178 **2. Model-to-map agreement metrics** (when an atomic model is available),
179 including *d_model*, *d_model_b0*, *d_fsc_model_0*, *d_fsc_model_0143*, and

180 $d_{fsc_model_05}$, which quantify the correspondence between the atomic model
181 and the cryo-EM map.

182 **3. Model-derived parameters**, like $b_iso_overall$ that reflect overall model
183 quality [15].

184 Together, these metrics offer an integrated and quantitative framework for evaluating
185 the cryo-EM reconstruction quality through combined map statistics, model-map
186 correlation metrics, and overall map and model quality. To facilitate interpretation, a
187 description of the *phenix.mtriage* metrics, along with their interpretation, is provided in
188 Table S1.

189 **2.2.2. Phenix.emringer**

190 *Phenix.emringer* [16], [17] is a tool that quantitatively evaluates the agreement between
191 an atomic model and a cryo-EM map by examining the density around side-chain χ_1
192 rotameric angles. It is particularly informative for high-resolution maps, where side-
193 chain features are well resolved. Beyond monitoring model-to-map fit in high-resolution
194 regions, the method is also sensitive to local map alterations associated with radiation
195 damage. The tool produces a small set of output statistics, with the EMRinger score as
196 the primary global metric and supplementary values, such as the maximum Z-score that
197 help contextualize the significance of side-chain density responses. As before, Table S2
198 presents a detailed overview of all *phenix.emringer* metrics, along with their definitions.

199 **2.2.3. Phenix.real_space_refine**

200 This Phenix tool is a refinement engine that optimizes atomic models directly against
201 cryo-EM maps using real-space target functions [13], [18], [19]. The method
202 simultaneously improves model-map agreement and maintains proper stereochemistry
203 by applying a comprehensive set of restraints, which prevent unrealistic distortions of

204 the model, while allowing conformational changes supported by the cryo-EM map.
205 During refinement, Phenix reports several quantitative metrics, which can be grouped
206 into two main categories:

207 **1. Model-to-map agreement metrics**, like *CC mask*, which assess how well the
208 atomic model fits the experimental density map [13], [20].

209 **2. Geometric validation metrics [13]**, including *clashscore*, *Ramachandran*
210 *statistics (outliers, allowed, favored)*, and *Rotamer statistics (outliers, allowed,*
211 *favored)*, which evaluate the stereochemical quality of the refined model.

212 Together, these metrics, summarized in Table S3, provide a broad evaluation of the
213 refinement outcomes and help ensure that the atomic model remains consistent with
214 both the cryo-EM map and stereochemical principles.

215 **2.2.4. Q-scores**

216 The Q-score is a quantitative parameter that assesses the resolvability of individual
217 atoms in cryo-EM maps [14], [21]. In general, Q-scores are calculated for each
218 individual atom; however, they can also be averaged at different levels: across all atoms
219 in a model (*average Q-score*), or over specific atom groups, such as amino acid residues
220 in proteins or nucleotides in nucleic acids (*per-residue* and *per-nucleotide Q-scores*
221 respectively).

222 **2.3. Metrics generation workflow**

223 The first step in our workflow is to generate post-processed maps using the methods
224 described in Section 2.1. *Post-processing methods*. In our dataset, cryo-EM maps
225 belonging to the test set have already been processed with each of these approaches.
226 However, if a user wishes to calculate metrics for a map that has not been post-

227 processed, our workflow is designed to do it automatically by providing the map's
228 EMD-ID. In this case, the user needs to have installed the corresponding software. For
229 more information, see our GitHub repository.

230 Once the post-processed maps are either provided in our dataset or obtained by the
231 user, the calculation of the metrics can proceed. To facilitate the objective evaluation of
232 different post-processing methods, we computed a comprehensive set of quantitative
233 structural metrics describing the quality of the maps. For this analysis, we computed
234 four validation metrics, each associated with a specific tool: *phenix.mtriage*,
235 *phenix.emringer*, *phenix.real_space_refine*, and Q-scores (explained in Section 2.2.
236 *Metrics*). We performed two distinct analysis workflows, as summarized in Figure 1:

237 **1. Refined route.** In this workflow, the process began with
238 *phenix.real_space_refine*, generating a refined PDB, which was subsequently
239 used as input for the calculation of all remaining metrics (*phenix.mtriage*,
240 *phenix.emringer*, and Q-scores). The order of execution among these latter tools
241 does not affect their results.

242 **2. Non-refined route.** In this case, the initial, unrefined model was used directly
243 for the computation of *phenix.mtriage*, *phenix.emringer*, and Q-scores, followed
244 by the execution of *phenix.real_space_refine*. The refined PDB obtained in this
245 second route was not employed for further analysis.

246 In Supplementary Data section *SI. Additional details on metrics generation workflow*,
247 we provide additional details on the procedures employed, including the issues
248 encountered during the execution of specific metrics and the solutions implemented to
249 address them.

250 **2.4. Data availability and information**

251 We curated a comprehensive dataset of cryo-EM density maps acquired via single-
252 particle analysis from EMDB. The corresponding atomic structures were retrieved from
253 the PDB database in PDB format, and the most recent EMDB search was conducted on
254 September 18, 2025.

255 The dataset was constructed using unprocessed half-maps, rather than using the full
256 maps deposited in EMDB. This decision was motivated by the fact that many full maps
257 are usually sharpened and masked, which could introduce bias in subsequent analyses.
258 Pairs of identified half-maps were then averaged to generate unprocessed reference
259 maps (average maps) in MRC format, preserving the overall signal while reducing
260 random noise. This process yielded a total of 5,500 half-maps and 2,750 average maps,
261 which served as the foundation for all subsequent post-processing and metric
262 evaluations.

263 To ensure data quality and consistency, we filtered the complete collection of
264 cryo-EM entries to generate a curated subset that met the following criteria: (1)
265 resolution ranging from 2 to 7Å; (2) the presence of one and only one associated atomic
266 model for each EMDB ID; (3) spatial correlation between the map and its atomic model
267 higher than 0.6; and (4) availability of half-maps. After applying these filtering criteria,
268 the dataset was reduced to a curated subset of maps, resulting in fewer half-maps and
269 average maps than in the original collection. However, this preliminary dataset contains
270 a high degree of redundancy, which could potentially bias evaluation procedures. To
271 mitigate this issue, we applied a redundancy control procedure to protein chains before
272 dividing the dataset into training, validation, and testing subsets. We considered that
273 two EMDB entries were equivalent if they share at least one sequence belonging to the

274 same 30% sequence identity cluster. Under this equivalence criterion, only one
275 representative per cluster was included in the validation and testing sets to avoid bias,
276 whereas up to five representatives were allowed in the training set to increase its
277 diversity and size. This decision was justified by the intrinsic variability of cryo-EM
278 reconstructions, where maps of the same protein can exhibit distinct statistical
279 characteristics [4].

280 As a result, the curated dataset contained a total of 1,186 maps and was
281 partitioned into training, validation, and testing sets, comprising approximately 70%,
282 15%, and 15% of the maps, respectively. The complete list of EMDB entries used in
283 each subset is available in a JSON file in our GitHub repository. This partitioning
284 enables the reproducible development and benchmarking of DL-models for cryo-EM
285 map post-processing and analysis.

286 Beyond the original half-maps, average maps, and atomic models, the dataset
287 also includes all post-processed maps from the test set, generated using the methods
288 described in Section 2.1. *Post-processing methods*. The dataset additionally provides all
289 metrics obtained in our workflow (see Section 2.3. *Metrics generation workflow*).
290 Specifically, it includes: (1) the auxiliary files generated during the execution of each
291 validation tool; (2) the complete set of metrics computed for the 178 test maps; (3) a
292 CSV file compiling all metric values across post-processing methods; (4) a JSON file
293 summarizing the statistics used for generating the figures and quantitative evaluations;
294 and (5) the JSON file for each map, containing metadata such as the associated PDB
295 structure, resolution, and other map-specific characteristics. Together, these resources
296 ensure full reproducibility of the analyses reported here.

297 **3. Metrics comparison**

298 Individual plots of each metric were generated for both unrefined and refined atomic
299 models against post-processed maps. This approach enables a clear visualization of how
300 each post-processing method when coupled with *phenix.real_space_refine* influences
301 each structural metric and consequently allows assessing the impact of post-processing
302 on both map and model quality. Moreover, the scripts provided in our GitHub
303 repository allow users to reproduce these plots and quantify the effect of refinement.

304 These plots were obtained from the test set, after excluding any maps that
305 overlap with the training and validation sets of CryoTEN or EMReady, resulting in a
306 final subset of 128 maps. This approach ensures that the generated plots remain
307 unbiased by training data, thereby providing an objective evaluation of the effect of
308 post-processing on map and model quality. However, if desired, our scripts allow the
309 generation of corresponding plots from the full set of 178 test maps without applying
310 this filter.

311 For clarity, we show here representative metrics per validation tool (Figures 2-
312 5), while all the other metrics are provided in Supplementary Data. Specifically, Figure
313 2 presents boxplots of the *d_fsc_model_05* metric from *phenix.mtriage*, summarizing
314 the performance of the different post-processing methods under two conditions: using a
315 refined model (top panels) or using the original deposited model (*not_refine*, bottom
316 panels). The panels labeled as *masked* display values calculated from the map masked
317 around the atomic model generated internally by *phenix.mtriage*, whereas *unmasked*
318 panels report the results using the full map. Each boxplot summarizes the distribution
319 across all analyzed cases, with the median represented by the central line, the
320 interquartile range shown by the box edges, and whiskers marking the overall span of

321 the data; points outside these limits correspond to outliers. A complementary table
322 (Table S4) in the Supplementary Data reports the mean, median, and percentile values
323 of *d_fsc_model_05* for each method. Additionally, boxplots for the remaining
324 *phenix.mtriage* metrics are provided in Supplementary Section S3. *Phenix.mtriage*
325 *figures*.

326 Figure 3 focuses on the *EMRinger score* obtained with *phenix.emringer*. As
327 before, the boxplots compare refined and unrefined (*not_refine*) models. As with the
328 previous metric, a complementary table (Table S5) is provided in the Supplementary
329 Data, detailing mean, median, and percentile statistics of the *EMRinger score* for each
330 method to facilitate a more quantitative evaluation. Additionally, boxplots for the
331 remaining *phenix.emringer* metrics are provided in Supplementary Section S4.
332 *Phenix.emringer figures*.

333 In the case of quality metrics derived from *phenix.real_space_refine*, it is
334 important to note that the refinement process generates an output file that records, at
335 each iteration, updated validation metrics such as *CC mask*, and *clashscore*, among
336 others (see Section 2.2.3. *Phenix.real_space_refine*). We specifically analyzed the
337 values from the first iteration (*before_refine*), reflecting the initial state of the model
338 prior to any adjustments, and the last iteration (*after_refine*), corresponding to the fully
339 refined model. Comparing these two conditions allows an objective assessment of how
340 refinement improves model-to-map fit throughout the iterative process. As shown in
341 Figure 4, we illustrate this effect using the *CC mask* metric, displaying its distribution
342 before and after refinement for each post-processing method. A corresponding table
343 (Table S6) in the Supplementary Data provides the mean, median, and percentile values
344 of *CC mask*, complementing the visual comparison with quantitative metrics.

345 Additionally, boxplots for the remaining *phenix.real_space_refine* metrics are provided
346 in Supplementary Section S5. *Phenix.real_space_refine* figures.

347 Finally, Figure 5 shows the distribution of *average Q-score* for refined and
348 unrefined models, displayed in two separate plots. As in the previous cases, a
349 complementary table (Table S7) is provided in the Supplementary Data, detailing mean,
350 median, and percentile values of the *average Q-score* for each method to support a more
351 quantitative comparison.

352 In addition to the global analysis, our code can also compute and represent *per-*
353 *residue Q-scores*, distinguishing between backbone (*Q_BackBone*) and side-chain
354 atoms (*Q_SideChain*) for specific cases. This level of analysis enables residue-by-
355 residue inspection of map-model agreement and facilitates the identification of regions
356 where the density may be poorly resolved or where the model may be misfitted,
357 resulting in reduced structural accuracy [21]. As representative examples, we include
358 this analysis for EMD-31911 [22], and EMD-15072 [23]. Figure 6 and Figure 7
359 collectively illustrate the effect of refinement across all post-processing methods
360 evaluated. Specifically, Figure 6 shows the distribution of *per-residue Q-scores* for
361 refined models, whereas Figure 7 presents the corresponding results for unrefined
362 models. Blue points correspond to *Q_BackBone*, while orange points represent
363 *Q_SideChain* values, with each point reflecting the agreement between the electron
364 density in the map and the atomic position for a specific residue. The horizontal lines
365 indicate the expected statistical behaviour of Q-scores as a function of resolution: the
366 solid black line denotes *Q_peak*, representing the most frequently observed Q-score at a
367 given resolution (usually the map global FSC resolution), while the dashed and dotted
368 lines mark the 95% confidence interval bounds (*Q_low_95%* and *Q_high_95%*),
369 defining the range where most residues are expected to fall [21].

370 *4. Discussion*

371 The dataset and evaluation framework outlined in this work address a central challenge
372 in cryo-EM map post-processing: the lack of standardized, reproducible, and
373 quantitative resources for assessing how different enhancement strategies influence both
374 map quality and model-to-map agreement. Despite the emergence of many post-
375 processing algorithms, as those based on DL, in recent years, the domain still lacks a
376 cohesive benchmark for researchers to assess new methods in a controlled and
377 comparable manner. Our work directly responds to this end by providing a curated
378 collection of raw maps, along with their associated atomic models, and an extensive
379 range of precomputed validation metrics created through a completely reproducible
380 workflow.

381 Moreover, developers of new map enhancement methods can use the curated
382 dataset proposed here for training and evaluation of their models, directly contrasting
383 their results with the metrics presented here. Importantly, this allows the direct training
384 of their models without requiring previous work of preparing and curating the map
385 dataset. Moreover, our dataset enables the evaluation of novel methods by comparison
386 with state-of-the-art post-processing approaches without requiring the installation or the
387 generation of new maps, as we provide post-processed versions of all test-set maps. If
388 users wish to evaluate additional maps, they need to install the corresponding software
389 and simply add the new map IDs to the test list.

390 A major advantage of our dataset is that every map —raw data, and post-
391 processed— is produced under consistently uniform computational conditions. This
392 guarantees that the differences noted in the validation metrics stem from inherent
393 characteristics of the post-processing techniques. By working directly with half-maps

394 and systematically generating average maps, we avoid inconsistencies caused by pre-
395 processed EMDB maps and ensure that all methods are applied to the same unbiased
396 starting data, making the result easy to compare.

397 The metric-generation workflow adds an additional layer of consistency to the
398 dataset. By combining four validation tools —*phenix.mtriage*, *phenix.emringer*,
399 *phenix.real_space_refine*, and Q-scores— we offer a comprehensive perspective on
400 map and model quality. To capture the influence of atomic model refinement on these
401 metrics, we computed each metric under two conditions: using the refined atomic model
402 and using the initial, unrefined model. Comparing these two workflows helps determine
403 whether observed improvements stem from the post-processing itself or from the
404 refinement step. This distinction is important, since post-processing methods can
405 modify density features in ways that directly impact the refinement and, consequently,
406 the resulting model-quality metrics. To facilitate this analysis, our workflow also
407 enables users to generate plots analogous to those shown in Figures 2-7.

408 Finally, our dataset also includes a rigorous redundancy control strategy based
409 on sequence-identity clustering, ensuring that the training, validation, and testing sets
410 are mutually exclusive. This is particularly important for DL-based methods, which are
411 sensitive to redundancy leakage. At the same time, it provides full transparency and
412 reproducibility by including all intermediate files generated during metric computation
413 (see Section 2.3. *Metrics generation workflow*), along with CSV and JSON summaries.
414 This design enables researchers to track each reported value back to the specific
415 combination of map, atomic model, and refinement stage from which it was obtained.
416 Although the dataset is not meant to directly compare post-processing methods, the
417 collection of metrics creates a solid quantitative baseline for evaluating new algorithms.

418 **5. Conclusion**

419 We have presented a rigorous and reproducible framework for the evaluation of cryo-
420 EM post-processing methods. By integrating half-maps, average maps, atomic models,
421 post-processed volumes, and an extensive set of precomputed validation metrics, the
422 proposed dataset provides a comprehensive resource for assessing how enhancement
423 techniques influence structural information at both global and local levels.

424 A central contribution of our work is the standardized protocol for metric
425 calculation, which enables objective and reproducible comparisons across different
426 approaches. Additionally, the dataset includes mutually exclusive training, validation,
427 and test subsets which are specifically designed to train new post-processing models
428 under unbiased conditions.

429 Although the current version of the dataset includes metrics generated with a
430 specific selection of post-processing methods, our workflow can be extended with
431 minimal effort. Researchers may incorporate new algorithms, compute the same
432 metrics, and compare their results with those provided in the dataset. This flexibility
433 enables expansion of the comparative framework beyond the methods initially included.

434 As cryo-EM advances towards higher resolution and increased throughput,
435 resources like this may help improve the precision of emerging post-processing methods
436 and facilitate a deeper understanding of biological structures.

437 **6. Data availability**

438 The dataset will be made publicly available in a Dataverse repository.

439 **7. Code availability**

440 The source code used for the calculation of the metrics will be made publicly available
441 in a GitHub repository.

442 **8. Competing interests**

443 The authors declare no competing interests.

444 **9. Acknowledgments**

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448 **10. Author contributions**

449 Javier Vargas and Rubén Sánchez-García contributed to the conceptualization of the
450 work and methodology. Javier Vargas supervised students and contributed to project
451 administration. Andreea V. Florea and Javier Vargas developed the software and
452 contributed to the writing and revision of the manuscript. Águeda Sierra and Jose
453 Antonio Gómez-Pedrero contributed to the writing and critical revision of the
454 manuscript.

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457 **Figures**

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463 **Figure 1. Diagram of the metrics generation workflow.** The 'refined' branch
464 represents Route 1, and the 'not refined' branch represents Route 2. Steps shown as
465 ovals are associated with *phenix.real_space_refine*, whereas rectangular nodes represent
466 all other metric-calculation steps.

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477 **Figure 2. Distribution of the $d_{fsc_model_05}$ metric for different density map post-**
478 **processing methods.** Evaluated using refined models (top panels) and unrefined models
479 (bottom panels, *not_refine*). *Masked* panels show results for maps masked around the
480 atomic model, whereas *unmasked* panels correspond to full-map calculation. Each box
481 plot summarizes the distribution across our filtered subset of 128 maps, displaying the
482 median, quartiles, overall range, and outliers, plotted as dots; enabling an evaluation of
483 how refinement and masking impact the model-to-map resolution. Boxplot labels
484 correspond to post-processing methods as follows: dem: DeepEMhancer, emr2:
485 EMReady2, emr: EMReady.

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497 **Figure 3. Distribution of the *EMRinger* score metric for different density map post-**
498 **processing methods.** Comparison of *EMRinger* score distribution across our filtered
499 subset of 128 maps for refined models (top panel) and unrefined models (bottom panel,
500 *not_refine*). Each boxplot displays the median, quartiles, overall spread, and outliers;
501 enabling a direct assessment of how refinement influences model-to-map agreement.
502 Boxplot labels correspond to post-processing methods as follows: dem: DeepEMhancer,
503 emr2: EMReady2, emr: EMReady.

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514 **Figure 4. Distribution of the *CC mask* metric for different density map post-**
515 **processing methods.** Distribution of *CC mask* values from *phenix.real_space_refine*
516 using respective post-processed maps for the first refinement iteration (*before_refine*),
517 and the final iteration (*after_refine*) across our filtered subset of 128 maps. Each
518 boxplot shows the median, quartiles, overall spread, and outliers; enabling evaluation of
519 how refinement influences map-model agreement within the masked region. Boxplot
520 labels correspond to post-processing methods as follows: dem: DeepEMhancer, emr2:
521 EMReady2, emr: EMReady.

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533 **Figure 5. Distribution of the average Q -score across different density map post-**
534 **processing methods.** Average Q -score distributions for refined and unrefined models
535 computed over our filtered subset of 128 maps. Each boxplot shows the median,
536 quartiles, overall spread, and outliers, allowing assessment of how refinement and post-
537 processing influence local model-to-map agreement. Boxplot labels correspond to post-
538 processing methods as follows: dem: DeepEMhancer, emr2: EMReady2, emr:
539 EMReady.

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548 **Figure 6. Distribution of *per-residue Q-scores* for backbone atoms ($Q_{BackBone}$, in**
 549 **blue) and side-chain atoms ($Q_{SideChain}$, in orange) for refined models fitted to**
 550 **maps EMD-31911(resolution 2.29Å), and EMD-15072 (resolution 3.0Å). Results are**
 551 **shown for the different post-processing methods: average maps (a, i), CryoTEN (b, j),**
 552 **DeepEMhancer (c, k), EMReady (d, l), EMReady v2 (e, m), LocScale (f, n), LocScale***
 553 **(g, o), and LocSpiral (h, p). Horizontal reference lines correspond to resolution-**
 554 **calibrated Q-scores: the solid line indicates the expected Q_{peak} at the given nominal**
 555 **resolution, while dashed and dotted lines mark 95% confidence interval ($Q_{low_95\%}$**
 556 **and $Q_{high_95\%}$).**

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566 **Figure 7. Distribution of per-residue Q-scores for backbone atoms ($Q_{BackBone}$, in**
 567 **blue) and side-chain atoms ($Q_{SideChain}$, in orange) for unrefined models fitted to**
 568 **maps EMD-31911(resolution 2.29Å), and EMD-15072 (resolution 3.0Å). Different**
 569 **post-processing methods were compared: average maps (a, i), CryoTEN (b, j),**
 570 **DeepEMhancer (c, k), EMReady (d, l), EMReady v2 (e, m), LocScale (f, n), LocScale***
 571 **(g, o), and LocSpiral (h, p). Horizontal reference lines represent resolution-calibrated Q-**
 572 **scores (Q_{peak} , $Q_{low_95\%}$, $Q_{high_95\%}$).**

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